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Report on connecting E³UDRES² ecosystems: strategy and implementation plan | Date 30-Sep-2025

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Abstract

The E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem is a multi-level framework connecting universities, researchers, businesses, and communities to foster co-creation, innovation, and democratic governance. Structured around the roles of Pillars, Nexus, Sparks, and Waves, the ecosystem enables strategic leadership, collaboration, experimentation, and societal impact across three key Nodes: Shared R&I, Open Practices & Citizen Science, and HR.

This document presents a strategic model and an implementation plan for the HR Node, developed in WP6 during the last period and taking into account the work done in the project, as well as consultations with other WPs. It aligns institutional human resource development with European principles, such as HRS4R, the Charter & Code, and OTM-R. The plan outlines eight core actions designed to improve researchers' career development, training, mobility, and inclusion. These initiatives adapt to local contexts and are supported by a participatory sociocratic decision-making process.

By integrating strategic planning, cross-institutional collaboration, and innovation-driven practices, the E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem offers a holistic approach to building inclusive, transparent, and sustainable research cultures across Europe.

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

List of project participants

Participant organisation name	Country
Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS)	PT
St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS)	AT
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)	HU
Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT)	RO
University Colleges Leuven Limburg (UCLL)	BE
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA)	LV

Abbreviated terms

AI – Artificial intelligence

DEI – Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion

E³UDRES² – Engaged European Entrepreneurial University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions

EU – European Union

HEIs – Higher Education Institutions

HR – Human Resources

HRS4R – Human Resources Strategy for Research

OTM-R – Open Transparent and Merit-based Recruitment of Researchers

R1 to R4 – Stages of the careers of the researchers

R&I – Research and Innovation

WP – Work Package

Executive Summary

The E³UDRES² Research and Innovation (R&I) Ecosystem is a forward-thinking, multi-level framework designed to encourage collaboration, transparency, and democratic decision-making among European higher education institutions. This ecosystem connects education, research, business, and society through three strategic nodes of practice: Shared R&I, Open Practices and Citizen Science, and Human Resources. Each node operates within a dynamic structure consisting of Pillars (strategic leadership), Nexus (collaboration and knowledge sharing), Sparks (innovation and experimentation) and Waves (impact and dissemination).

This report focuses on the Human Resources Node, which plays a critical role in promoting ethical, inclusive, and supportive environments for researchers at all stages of their career (R1–R4). Guided by European frameworks such as HRS4R, the Charter & Code, and OTM-R principles, the Node has developed an Implementation Plan comprising eight concrete actions. These include career guidance systems, training needs assessments, transparent and open recruitment practices, support for diversity and inclusion, mobility opportunities, and improvements to research environments.

The governance model is based on sociocratic decision-making, which means that all stakeholders are involved in the creation and implementation of strategies. Collaboration within and between nodes is enabled through structured meetings, shared infrastructure, and a commitment to transparency and equity.

Rather than prescribing a one-size-fits-all approach, the ecosystem encourages partners to adapt the proposed actions to their institutional, national, and regional contexts. With built-in flexibility, cross-institutional learning, and strong alignment to European values, the E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem aims to become a benchmark for creating impactful and future-ready academic environments throughout Europe.

1. Introduction

The E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem is a dynamic, multi-level framework that connects education, research, innovation, and society across its partner institutions. The HR Node is one of the three Nodes of this ecosystem, aligning institutional HR policies with key European frameworks.

The HR Node's Implementation Plan transforms strategy into concrete action through specific efforts across all four roles—Pillars, Nexus, Sparks, and Waves, and it consists of eight key actions: 1) implementing structured career guidance for researchers at all levels (R1–R4) with clear progression criteria and mentoring support; 2) systematically identifying training needs and developing individualized training plans; 3) ensuring wide dissemination and equal access to training programs; 4) creating flexible short- and long-term mobility opportunities for collaboration and co-creation; 5) aligning recruitment policies with OTM-R principles to guarantee open, transparent, and merit-based hiring; 6) embedding diversity, equity, and inclusion strategies into institutional practice; 7) strengthening ethical frameworks and research integrity through guidelines, training, and monitoring; and 8) improving the research environment by enhancing infrastructure, promoting flexible work arrangements, and integrating well-being into strategic planning. Together, these actions serve as a roadmap for building a fair, supportive, and future-ready research culture across E³UDRES².

It is crucial to outline that the implementation plan presented in this report is advisory rather than mandatory. Institutions are encouraged to adapt the actions to their own national regulations, institutional strategies, and local contexts, rather than implementing them all uniformly. Furthermore, external factors—such as changing funding opportunities, rapid advances in AI and digital tools, and changing European and national policy frameworks—will influence how these measures are prioritised and applied, requiring continuous monitoring and agile adaptation.

2. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Human Resources Node Strategy Vision, Mission and Principles

The Human Resources Node within the E³UDRES² alliance is established to encourage the implementation of the Joint Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R), in accordance with the national legislation. This Node promotes ethical, inclusive, and transparent research and innovation ecosystem aligned with the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for Recruitment, The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and other EU level strategic and planning documents. It fosters career development, international mobility, and institutional collaboration to empower researchers across diverse institutions and contexts. To effectively address the challenges of a rapidly changing environment, we should strive to create a stable working framework that enables us to respond with the necessary agility to anticipated changes in the workforce, labour market, artificial intelligence, and other emerging factors.

The strategic design of the Shared HR Node is informed by insights from the preparatory deliverables (D6.1–D6.3) and the WP6 Milestone, which involved obtaining the HR Excellence in Research Award (please see Appendix No. 1 for more information about the application process). These documents collectively identified structural gaps, barriers, and opportunities that must be addressed to make the HR and Institutional Development system both effective and sustainable. Taken together, they highlight eight key areas for intervention.

MISSION

To promote/support E³UDRES² as a leading network of progressive, researcher-friendly universities that champion equitable career development, international mobility, and ethical research practices. Through collaboration and shared values, we envision a research landscape where all scholars—regardless of background—have the resources, opportunities, and support needed to flourish professionally, drive innovation, and create meaningful societal impact.

VISION

By empowering researchers and institutions through an inclusive and transparent E³UDRES² Joint HRS4R Strategy, we accelerate the transformation into Europe's multi-institutional hub for research and innovation in smart and sustainable regions.

Principles

- *Transparency* – Ensure open, merit-based recruitment and performance evaluation processes across institutions.

- *Integrity* – Uphold ethical conduct, academic honesty, and responsibility in all aspects of researcher support and management, as well as foster an environment that enables meaningful, impactful work and feedback.
- *Equity & Inclusion* – Promote fair treatment, equal opportunities, and inclusive practices for all researchers, regardless of background.
- *Professional Growth* – Support continuous agility through tailored training, mentorship, and interdisciplinary collaboration while addressing the impact of generative AI on the organisation of work.
- *Collaboration* – Foster cross-institutional cooperation and shared HR practices to enhance mobility, learning, and innovation, while exploring the use of AI to strengthen collaboration, facilitate knowledge sharing, and support more effective communication across the alliance.
- *Well-being* – Provide supportive working conditions, flexible policies, and a healthy work-life balance for researchers, focusing on reducing stress and maintaining well-being.

2.1. Background deliverables and roadmap to the strategy

In the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, the methodology for developing the HR sharing strategy builds on the findings of the previous deliverables (D6.1–D6.3) and the WP6 milestone. These preparatory steps provided the empirical evidence and analytical frameworks that form the foundation of this strategic and implementation plan.

2.1.1. Roadmap of preparatory steps

D6.1 – Status report on E³UDRES² partners' human resources for research

- Survey of 405 researchers across six partner universities profiled demographics, academic roles, research workload, mobility, and compliance with Charter & Code principles, to assess the current status in the field of HR.

→ Provided the baseline about HR situation in each institution and research/academic staff profiles.

D6.2. – Status report on E³UDRES² R&I ecosystems

- Survey and interviews with 92 stakeholders across six partner universities mapped the human resources and research & innovation ecosystems, producing HR and R&I SWOT analyses.
- *Strengths*: Diverse educational backgrounds, transparent recruitment processes, strong ethical frameworks, accredited quality systems, active international collaborations, flexible work arrangements, and a growing culture of applied research.
- *Weaknesses*: High teaching/research/administrative workloads limiting research time, fragmented research management, limited doctoral programmes, inconsistent funding, gender imbalances, HR capacity gaps, and weak internal communication on R&I opportunities.

- *Opportunities*: EU and national frameworks defining career stages, funding calls to strengthen research infrastructure, demand for applied and mission-driven research, technological advancements (AI, data), and international collaboration potential.
- *Threats*: Funding volatility, competition for skilled researchers, demographic ageing, risk of burnout, political/geopolitical uncertainty, and the need to keep pace with rapid technological change.

→ Provided a comprehensive HR and R&I ecosystem baseline, outlining strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats, as well as guiding institutional strategies for researcher career development, improved cooperation, and futureproofing of research and innovation capacity.

D6.3 – E³UDRES² Joint Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)

- Six partner universities developed a joint strategy to establish a joint, researcher-friendly HR framework aligned with the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct.
- *Core values*: academic integrity, research freedom, transparency, professional growth, supportive working conditions, equality, and diversity inclusion.
- *Key actions*: structured career guidance and mentoring, individualised development plans, mobility opportunities beyond Erasmus+, harmonised recruitment templates and OTM-R practices, diversity audits and leadership training, interdisciplinary ethics training, and flexible work arrangements.
- *Institutional adaptation*: each partner integrates the joint actions into its own context while maintaining alliance-wide coherence.

→ Provides a shared long-term commitment to improving research careers, enhancing inclusivity, strengthening ethics, and fostering a sustainable, attractive research environment across the alliance.

Synthesis:

Collectively, these deliverables provided the necessary data, analytical frameworks, and risk insights for D6.4. Previous deliverables ensure that the strategy is not only grounded in evidence and aligned with institutional and regional realities but also designed to overcome obstacles, minimise risks, and capitalise on opportunities for a sustainable and adaptable HR network.

2.2. Lessons learned and strategic directions

Throughout the Ent-r-e-novators project WP6, we've gained valuable insights into the role of human capital, the development of researcher careers, and the regional disparities in HR policies across Europe. These lessons have shaped our future strategy, emphasising the need to create inclusive and effective environments for researchers across Europe's diverse regions.

One of the most significant challenges WP6 encountered was the wide variation in HR practices and expectations between regions. As institutions in different countries have different frameworks for researcher mobility, career development, and inclusion, it became clear that a one-size-fits-all approach wouldn't work.

HR strategies must be regionally tailored, considering local labour market conditions, policies, and institutional cultures. Moving forward, we'll focus on flexible HR frameworks that enable us to address local needs while maintaining European objectives, ensuring equitable opportunities for all researchers across the continent.

A related challenge was the disparity in infrastructure and funding between regions. Some areas didn't have the resources to provide the same level of support for professional development or professional mobility as others. To overcome this, we'll prioritise regional collaboration, creating mobility pathways that allow researchers from less-resourced regions to tap into the more developed infrastructures available in other areas. This will ensure equitable access to research opportunities, regardless of the researchers' location.

Another area where we saw significant variation was in the career development opportunities offered to researchers. Some institutions struggled to establish clear career progression paths, while others lacked effective mentorship and training programs. To address this, we'll introduce clear career development frameworks that are adaptable to different regional and institutional contexts, ensuring that every researcher, regardless of their location, has access to structured career development, mentorship, and mobility opportunities.

Equally important was our focus on diversity, equality and inclusion (DEI). While some regions excelled in diversity and inclusion (D&I) initiatives—such as gender equality, social inclusion, and diverse talent recruitment—others faced significant cultural and institutional barriers. To ensure that DEI efforts are impactful, we'll integrate region-specific initiatives into our HR policies. This means not just creating universal DEI standards, but tailoring actions to the unique needs and challenges of each region, whether that's tackling gender inequality, improving disability access, or enhancing social inclusion efforts.

As we move forward, these lessons will guide us in shaping a strategy that is not only inclusive and regionally tailored but also sustainable. We recognise that regional differences must be acknowledged and addressed, and that by adapting HR practices and creating pathways for more equitable collaboration, we can ensure that all researchers—regardless of their location—have the opportunities they need to thrive.

At the same time, while we acknowledge regional differences, we also aim to move towards a more aligned HR strategy that fosters consistency and cohesion across all regions. This alignment will be achieved through the overarching ecosystem model, which will serve as the guiding framework for ensuring that each region can both contribute to and benefit from the shared strengths of the broader European research landscape.

As we implement structural changes, we remain committed to continuous learning and improvement, ensuring that feedback from all regions is integrated into the evolving strategy. This will enable us to remain responsive to emerging challenges and ensure that every researcher, regardless of location, has the necessary tools and opportunities to succeed.

3. The architecture of the open ecosystem for E³UDRES² R&I from the perspective of shared HR

3.1 Introduction

The E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem acts as a unifying framework that connects research, education, innovation, and regional development across the Alliance. It is structured around four interlinked roles — Pillars, Nexus, Sparks, and Waves — which together provide strategic orientation, coordinate operations, enable experimentation, and facilitate broad knowledge sharing. This role-based model ensures that the ecosystem remains adaptive, scalable, and focused on achieving meaningful impact.

Figure 1 presents the overall architecture of the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem, emphasising its multi-level design and the dynamic interaction between roles and nodes.

Figure 1 - E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem: Multi-Level Structure

As Deliverable D4.3 (WP4) provides a detailed description of the ecosystem model, including its governance, practice networks, and implementation principles, this chapter offers only a concise overview for the sake of consistency. The focus of the following sections is on WP6's specific contribution: the development of the Shared HR Node.

3.2. WP6 focus: The Shared HR Node

Within the broader ecosystem architecture, WP6 is dedicated to creating the Shared HR Node. This node transforms the overarching framework into a focused, operational pathway aimed at advancing human resources and researcher career development.

Table 1 outlines the four roles of the E³UDRES² ecosystem (Pillars, Nexus, Sparks, Waves), which equally form the foundation for the Shared HR Node. While the complete ecosystem design is detailed in Deliverable D4.3 (WP4), the table is included here to clarify how these roles are explicitly applied to strengthening HR management and researcher support.

Table 1 - Key roles in the Ecosystem model nodes

Role	Area of impact
Pillars	Provide strategic foresight and long-term thematic vision (Policy, EU policy alignment, ...)
Nexus	Serves as the collaborative center for dialogue, co-creation, and sociocratic decision-making. <i>Cross nexus sessions: to share output created in each node</i>
Sparks	Experimental units where interdisciplinary teams launch pilot projects.
Waves	Ensure dissemination, scaling, and systemic impact.
Core	Overarching Steering Board (accountables)

The more detailed governance structures and implementation mechanisms for the Shared HR Node are elaborated in Chapter 4 of this deliverable.

4. Core components of the roles and responsibilities for the Node HR

4.1. The Pillars: Strategic Governance in HR

The Pillars represent the foundation and strategic direction of the node. The Pillars comprise experts, coordinators, and representatives from key sectors/ organisations/ companies, guiding the development and implementation of policies and initiatives across practices connected to Human Resource management. The Pillars align institutional HR policies with European frameworks (e.g., HRS4R, Charter & Code, OTM-R).

The Pillars are responsible for:

- Define shared vision and ethical HR principles rooted in transparency, inclusivity, and academic freedom.
- Ensure institutional alignment with HRS4R goals, including open recruitment, equity, and structured career pathways
- Oversee institutional compliance with the European Charter for Researchers and other relevant frameworks.
- Set and oversee performance indicators for professional growth, inclusivity, work environment quality, and training.

Strategic Direction Provided by the Pillars:

Vision & Mission: To create an inclusive, ethical, and high-quality European research and innovation ecosystem that fosters innovation, mobility, professional and career development and integrity.

Shared Values: Academic integrity, freedom of research, transparency, equity, and support for career development.

Democratic Decision-Making: A democratic decision-making determines the strategic course and priority projects, integrating diverse themes.

4.2. The Nexus: Core of Collaboration and Development

The Nexus represents the operational heart of HR innovation—facilitating the development, testing, and exchange of HR practices and support services for R&I staff.

Key activities in the Nexus:

- Implement structured career development plans including mentorship, mobility opportunities, and professional evaluations.

- Create shared training modules for R&I staff.
- Co-creating and testing digital tools and platforms that support open practices and collaborative research. (RDM, ethics, etc.)
- Support cross-institutional exchanges on career guidance, mobility, and researcher development programs
- Pilot innovative onboarding tools, for example, with the use of AI, as well as researcher databases, and feedback systems
- Host interactive workshops and communities of practice focused on training, diversity, and an inclusive leadership environment. The Nexus plays a central role in accelerating the adoption of innovative practices and tools within the whole ecosystem
- Promote sociocratic principles for decision-making and reflective learning among HR professionals.

Strategy behind the nexus:

Collaboration & shared vision: HR teams co-create tools and policies that meet the diverse needs of institutions and R&I staff.

Innovation: Digital solutions (including AI, researcher portals, and mobility tools) and shared infrastructure drive systemic change.

Inclusion: HR services are co-designed with diversity/inclusion experts and aligned with inclusivity goals.

4.3. The Sparks: Local HR Initiatives & Networks

The Sparks are thematic or local HR-driven initiatives—pilots and working groups—that translate HR strategy into practical innovations and community impacts.

Key Sparks initiatives:

Working Groups on open recruitment, ethics and training, diversity & inclusion, and flexible work conditions.

Pilot Projects testing hybrid work models, reintegration after leave, or equity-focused mentorship programs, etc.

Mobility Schemes beyond Erasmus+, integrating targeted incentives, digital onboarding, and recognition systems.

Regional HR Collaborations are enhancing onboarding, infrastructure sharing, and cross-border career planning.

Support Networks for early-career researchers, international scholars, and underrepresented groups.

Strategy Behind the Sparks:

Project No 101071317

Strategic Networking: Leverage alliances between HR teams, ethics boards, gender equality units, and mobility teams.

Scalable Innovation: Develop toolkits, training systems, and templates for reuse across institutions.

Responsive Design: Ensure that practices reflect institutional realities, national regulations, and the needs of R&I staff.

4.4. The Waves: Ripple Effect of Impact and Innovation

The Waves reflect the systemic impact of the HR Node's work—extending improved HR practices into the broader ecosystem and contributing to the reform of structural research culture.

Key outcomes of the Waves:

Open & Transparent Recruitment: Institutionalised OTM-R policies increase fairness, diversity, and talent retention.

Career Growth: Structured, comparable frameworks allow researchers to navigate clear, inclusive development paths.

Inclusive Research Environments: Workplace surveys and DEI audits inform evolving HR practices and leadership training.

Enhanced Well-being: Institutions incorporate work-life balance, flexible policies, and reintegration programs to foster long-term sustainability.

European & Global Visibility: Improved hiring practices and shared databases (e.g., EURAXESS) broaden the reach of researchers.

Strategy Behind the Waves:

Societal Impact: Foster talent development aligned with Europe's smart, inclusive, and sustainable research agenda.

Dissemination: Use case studies, templates, and good practice libraries to inform other institutions and regions.

Policy Influence: Shape national and European debates on HR excellence through evidence-based HR transformation.

5. Implementation plan

Action No. 1: Implement career guidance for researchers

Roles & Responsibilities	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status
Pillars	EURAXESS - following international standards National EURAXESS Service Centres	Define a task and job description for each level to ensure that opportunities and tasks are clear for everyone, creating certainty of expectations and increased plannability.	Levels R1-R4 have high hurdles, so researchers stagnate at these career levels. The pyramid narrows towards the top, so advancement depends on available positions.	EURAXESS offers career support services at various levels, enabling individuals to continue their careers at other universities through international mobility, based on their qualifications.	The basis of the career model is present in all participating universities, with individual versions being implemented in accordance with national laws and options.
	R1: Researchers conducting research under supervision, before or during their PhD studies R2: Researchers with a PhD or equivalent; not yet fully independent but recognised for their competence R3: Researchers who work independently, lead their own research projects, are familiar with the funding landscape and can potentially acquire funding R4: Researchers who have achieved (and are holding) a leading position within their field,	Examples for evaluation criteria: - Number of Publications - (Inter)national networking in projects - Conference participation (speaker?) - Amount of funding received - Definition of small/medium/large projects - Defined strategic fields	The importance of a doctorate for researchers is an essential academic career goal; however, it is not consistently assessed as a criterion for respective career stages, regardless of career levels (R1-R4) or employment types (e.g., permanent positions versus visiting lecturers). A doctorate is generally a very demanding task, especially when working simultaneously. In some fields, obtaining a doctoral degree at the national level can be challenging and may not	Networking and partnerships with (international) universities to highlight doctoral programs and supervisors. Longer-term contracts to alleviate the constant pressure to deliver consistently. The involvement of researchers in teaching brings in contemporary research results and creates an additional field of activity. Long-term partnerships with funding bodies and industry,	Within the framework of European accreditations and initiatives, comparable career levels are decisive.

	recognised for their contributions and ability to lead		<p>always be advisable in every faculty or university. In some fields, obtaining a PhD at the national level can be a challenging endeavour. Furthermore, a doctorate is not generally appropriate for all researchers or offers added value beyond a career model.</p> <p>Pure researchers have only one leg to stand on and can hardly gain experience in teaching or practical fields within the economy.</p> <p>If research funding is not forthcoming, there is an existential risk.</p> <p>Dependence on research funding can pose a risk to research freedom</p>	<p>as well as publicising strategic research fields.</p> <p>Preparation of qualification agreements with PhD students to plan management alongside the research task</p>	
	Describe and adapt R1-R4 levels to ensure a clear understanding of the basement for all researchers. This also includes equivalent options for a PhD or criteria to lead research projects of different sizes. Description of leadership skills that R3 and R4 persons acquire	The job profiles for R1-R4 define clear guidelines along key performance indicators to ensure objectivity and development steps.	Young researchers cannot lead representative projects because higher levels require this - the bottleneck.	A development path can be accompanied by a catalogue of criteria, supported by qualification agreements.	Harmonisation of criteria, options and requirements would be a viable option.
Nexus	Creation of a career model at all participating universities, aligned with EURAXESS. Accompanying frameworks (e.g., the OTMR strategy) ensure objectivity and	A comprehensive description of equivalences and harmonisation of criteria for career levels could be	The individual needs of universities are being overshadowed by a common approach, resulting in the loss of precision in	Supporting researchers is subject to a set of similar challenges across all participating universities.	Implementation of career models initiated via HRS4R and introduced in different versions.

	comparability across institutions beyond the individual.	initiated as a strategic position paper.	the respective university's development management within the national framework.		
Sparks	<p>Definition of a core of required, desired, and optional requirements for researchers at participating universities of applied sciences for the respective career levels.</p> <p>A mentoring program between the participating universities of applied sciences through the nomination of experts from the faculties.</p> <p>Joint job pool for defined subject areas to strengthen researcher mobility through temporary employment.</p>	<p>In addition to scientific (teaching & research) criteria, a second focus on career levels could be added, emphasising experience in business and practice, to differentiate from traditional universities and their basic research.</p>	<p>Accusations of non-scientific thinking from a purely academic perspective.</p> <p>An additional requirement for researchers that could further increase the pressure to deliver.</p>	<p>Business partners are also interested in fact-based decisions and seek rational solutions to problems.</p>	<p>In some participating universities, practical experience has already been integrated into their career model.</p>
Waves	<p>Continuous exchange and sharing of development measures and Best Practices</p> <p>Performance-oriented career model</p> <p>Appreciation of practical experience through inclusion in the career model</p> <p>Development of joint training measures for researchers</p> <p>Tenure-Track-Model as guidance to the next level</p>	<p>Entrenovators/HRS4R: Regular exchange formats & congresses</p> <p>Performance indicators are considered to varying degrees in the respective career models.</p> <p>Inclusion of practical experience alongside teaching and research</p> <p>Combining individual initiatives to set guidelines jointly e.g. Junior Professor to finish a PhD and get a Full-Professorship</p>	<p>Constant participation of all actors and consistent output is not guaranteed</p> <p>This approach does not fit into the value concept/framework of all participating universities of applied sciences.</p> <p>Acquiring practical experience could hinder scientific careers.</p> <p>Different focuses required (elective modules)</p> <p>The fit of the respective career models is not comprehensive</p>	<p>Clear setting of topics and leads and definition of expectations</p> <p>Question of methodology for measuring performance with different support options</p> <p>Joint definition of creditable practical experience</p> <p>All institutes offer proven and diverse continuing education programs and have similar needs for researchers.</p> <p>Widespread funding programs for young researchers</p>	<p>Ongoing</p> <p>Various approaches participating in AUS</p> <p>Different offers that need to be aligned (or adapted) to national requirements</p> <p>Existing in some AUS</p>

Action No. 2: Identify training needs to support individualised training and development plans

Roles & Responsibilities	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status
Pillars	Identify annual training needs in three key areas: specific scientific field, tailored training, research methodologies, and scientific project management.	Conduct a questionnaire among all researchers (all EUDRES partners) to identify their training needs. Additionally, focus groups and interviews may also be conducted.	Low participation of researchers in the survey.	The involvement and commitment of top management, and an individualised approach. Collaboration among partners.	Ongoing
Nexus	Create an annual plan to identify training needs in the three key areas: specific scientific field (tailored training), research methodologies, and scientific project management.	Validate the annual training program and schedule activities and resources according to the HEI's guidelines.	Lack of resources to implement the plan.	Involvement of top management.	Ongoing
Sparks	Engage EUDRES partners from the ecosystem in identifying training needs.	Hold two annual meetings with partners to evaluate the process of identifying training needs and the development plan.	Low commitment of partners.	Disseminate relevant information about the whole process to all partners.	Ongoing
Waves	Coordination and monitoring of the training needs assessment.	Quality assessment indicators.	Low commitment of the partners	Create a shared training needs methodology.	To be done

Action No. 3: Ensure widespread dissemination and access to training programs to promote transparency and equal opportunities

Roles & Responsibilities	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status
Pillars	The widespread availability of training programs that promote transparency and equal opportunities by the HEI. Development of training and development programs which reinforce continuous training in three key areas for researchers: their specific scientific field, research methodologies, and science (project) management	The training program will be disseminated annually, with additional monthly updates and applications to reinforce the information. Increase staff participation by 5% and expand training courses in scientific methodologies, project management, as well as tailored courses for each specific scientific/professional need.	There will always be some researchers who may feel that their training needs are not being adequately addressed. Lack of timely access to resources and budget for each field: training in scientific fields, scientific project management, and research methodologies.	Distribution of information throughout the institution while adhering to non-discrimination policies, the code of ethics, and principles of gender equality and diversity. The broad scope of training also mitigates. Collaboration within each institution and within the EUDRES.	Ongoing/In place Ongoing/In place
Nexus	Encourage the use of training assessment methodologies focused on personal and professional development. Create a learning platform. Establish a shared repository of research training materials, ensuring ongoing access that aligns with sustainability goals.	Emphasise training assessment as a tool for professional development and not only performance appraisal. In accordance with copyright regulations and ethics code, all training materials should be disseminated to stakeholders as educational resources.	Assessment can hinder participation due to difficulties in applying reliable methodologies. Additionally, confusion may arise between evaluation for development and assessment for control.	Positive recognition of all training. Increase in the number of new topics.	Ongoing Ongoing
Sparks	Training and Professional Development Programs developed within EUDRES focused on open science and citizen science, as well as other skills needed for implementing the Charter & Code.	Expand training programs by 5% to encompass a broader scientific scope, extending beyond the specific functions of researchers and emphasising their societal roles.	Quality versus quantity. Low participation. Lack of quality. Not integrated into career development.	Defining joint guidelines to avoid biases in the research and data collection.	Ongoing

	Implement training according to HRS4R.				
Waves	Promote participation in collaborative training activities (national and international/ in-person and online) Establish a certification system for EU researchers	Increase collaborative national and international collaborative training by 5% (other than ERASMUS+) Create an EUDRES Training Passport Create an EUDRES Training Passport	Language may be a barrier in some cases. Very limiting and/or standardised.	Online is a facilitator. Facilitates "mobility"/understanding	Ongoing

Action No. 4: Develop flexible short and long-term mobility options for cross-institutional knowledge exchange and co-creation opportunities within the E³UDRES² alliance

Roles & Responsibilities	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status
Pillars	Enhancing academic staff and researchers' mobility within the E ³ UDRES ² alliance, considering the E ³ UDRES ² mobility model	Increase in staff mobility inside the alliance.	Lack of identification of common projects motivating staff mobility	Operationalisation of E ³ UDRES ² alliance COE (centres of excellence)	Ongoing
	Allocating a budget for researchers' mobility within the alliance	Increase partners' budget for staff mobility (Erasmus+ or own funds) allocated to E ³ UDRES ² alliance.	Insufficient funds received by E ³ UDRES ² members from the Government and National Agencies	Improved planning of mobility, national initiatives to financially sustain European Universities alliances Provide support/training for writing project for alternative funding (ex., COST project)	Ongoing
Nexus	Dissemination of collaboration opportunities among E ³ UDRES ² partners	Monthly dissemination of collaboration opportunities	Lack of an office or an organisation in charge	Establishment of communication channels and designations of organisations in charge at the partner level.	To be done
	Continuously updating E ³ UDRES ² partners, the bank of researchers	Monthly invitations to develop and update the researcher's profile	Reduced interest and motivation	Better communications of the E ³ UDRES ² alliance's needs and opportunities	Ongoing

	Regular visits for enhancing collaboration	Yearly based staff mobility plan within the alliance	Hard to plan the visit several months in advance	Collecting mobility intentions and connecting them with collaboration opportunities.	To be done
	Mixed recruitment committees (and share job listing)				
Sparks	Establishment by each partner of information channels regarding E ³ UDRES ² collaboration opportunities	At least two regular information channels by the partner	Maintain updated information channels	Identification of contact and responsible persons for this activity at the institutional level	To be done
	Prioritisation of including E ³ UDRES ² members in project applications	All universities clearly communicate and make visible their thematic priorities when it comes to project proposals. For project proposals, each university establishes the priorities considering the themes of interest for the E ³ UDRES ² alliance.	Short deadlines, imposing the use of existing research networks	Fast communication opportunities, everyday use of a bank of researchers	Ongoing
Waves	Joint research activities	Increase in joint research activities (publications, research projects, research stages within the alliance)	Heterogeneity regarding motivation for research	Operationalisation of E ³ UDRES ² alliance COE (centres of excellence), identification of main research themes and coordinators at the institutional level.	To be done
	Joint recruitment policies	Regular monitoring of individual and joint HRS4R	Different time horizons for implementing HRS4R principles	Responsibilities of the HRS4R contact person in each university	ongoing / to be done
	Disseminating best practices	Dedicated website for HRS4R at the institutional level to disseminate best practices in terms of recruitment	Digital infrastructure capacity	Each institution should design a dedicated website or webpage for HRS4R.	ongoing / to be done

Action No. 5: Ensure alignment with OTM-R (Open, Transparent, and Merit-Based Recruitment) principles

Roles & Responsibilities	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status
Pillars	Develop and update recruitment guidelines based on OTM-R principles, as well as information materials for selection committees.	Leadership: ensure compliance in recruitment decisions.	Inconsistent application of OTM-R principles; there might be national legislation limitations	Standardised recruitment templates and procedures	Ongoing
	Leadership: ensure compliance in recruitment decisions.	Number of trained staff involved in recruitment.	Resistance to change in traditional recruitment practices	Internal audits	Ongoing
Nexus	Align recruitment policies and internal regulations with OTM-R principles.	Degree of alignment between HR and internationalisation strategies / Aligned recruitment internal regulations with OTM-R	Strategic misalignment or duplication of efforts; Resistance to changing recruitment procedures at the institutional level	Cross-departmental working groups; Dissemination of OTM-R principles	Ongoing
Sparks	Prepare OTM-R information materials, such as highlights and commonly developed robust infographics, that can be used in all institutions.	The number of staff connected to recruitment procedures reached through awareness materials should not be linked to "head count".	Low participation in awareness activities	Incentivize participation	Ongoing
	Promote OTM-R initiatives internally, e.g. share good practices	Time to hire	Limited visibility of OTM-R efforts	Incentivize participation	Ongoing
Waves	Coordinate a phased implementation plan and monitor progress.	Completion rate of each implementation wave	Implementation fatigue	Clear timeline and communication plan	Ongoing
	Leadership: approve and support each wave of implementation.		Lack of long-term commitment	Share success stories	Ongoing

Action No. 6: Ensure alignment with institutional-level Diversity and Gender Equality policies and share best practices

Roles & Responsibilities	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status
Pillars	Develop and implement comprehensive diversity and inclusion plans, taking into account national legislation and EU strategies.	Clear vision on diversity and inclusion translated towards actions	Other priorities within the institution itself, but also between the different partners of the consortium	Retaken in the institution's strategy Keeping enough freedom to consider the national specificities	Ongoing
	Ensure that everyone in the institution is informed about the strategy and plans related to this topic.	Communication plan in place	Limited attention to culture change and change management	Awareness of the culture change aspect	Ongoing
Nexus	Facilitate cross-institutional knowledge sharing	Having regular collaboration moments	Decrease in the degree of collaboration	Making sure that existing collaboration forms continue to exist even after the project phase	To start
	Translate plans into concrete actions which are monitored regularly	At least five institution-wide actions have been initiated that concretely translate the shared conceptual frameworks into practices aimed at inclusive, sustainable, and fair co-living	Actions not followed up on	Actions translated into KPI, which are regulated and monitored Follow up on the results of the surveys amongst employees Implementation plan	To start
Sparks	Connection with stakeholders beyond the consortium, within the broader society (e.g. organisations, etc).	At least one action/project related to diversity and inclusion for each institution in collaboration with external partners	Lack of in-house expertise on this topic. Not knowing the stakeholder landscape. Getting and keeping stakeholders on board	Gathering experts in cross-departmental workgroups around this topic	To start
					To start
Waves	Ensure that this is strategically anchored and embedded within the organisation.	A clear vision on diversity and inclusion is reiterated in the institution's strategy and translated into actions.	Inclusion is limited as a sole HR topic	Retaken in the institution's strategy Follow up on the survey results among employees. Implementation plan	Ongoing

	Think further than the institution itself. Elaborate on different opportunities to have a meaningful impact on this topic on a more societal level by connecting with research, education, and stakeholders outside the institution (companies, organisations...), e.g. in the form of research projects.	Degree of collaboration with a broader range of stakeholders on this topic	Lack of in-house expertise on this topic. Not knowing the stakeholder landscape. Getting and keeping stakeholders on board	Gathering experts in cross-departmental workgroups around this topic	To start
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Action No. 7: Ensure alignment with Ethical principles and promote integrity

Roles & Responsibilities	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status
Pillars	Every institution has a clear framework and guidelines in place regarding ethics and integrity. The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity can serve as a base.	Framework and guidelines in place	Resistance to adoption	Engage leadership and key stakeholders early in the process to gain their support.	Ongoing
Nexus	Alignment of these frameworks and policies between the different institutions, while also considering the specificities of each institution.	Degree of alignment and customisation	Overlooking institutional specificities	Identifying institution-specific needs and challenges. Creating a framework with core ethical principles which can be customized	Ongoing
	Making sure that this framework is known and applied by all employees	Communication plan in place	Lack of compliance monitoring	Compliance monitoring system with regular audits and feedback mechanisms	Ongoing
Sparks	New actions and projects are needed to fully incorporate these principles, such as developing e-learning materials, holding regular sessions to stay updated, and integrating them into the preboarding process for newcomers, among others.	Integration of these principles into institutional practices and processes	Resource constraints	Partnerships with external partners to share resources and expertise	To start

	Promote digital tools like plagiarism detection software and systems for ethical compliance monitoring.	Promotion and use of digital tools and ethical compliance	Resource constraints	Partnerships with external partners to share resources and expertise	To start
Waves	Regularly updating codes of ethics to reflect evolving research landscapes.	Frequency of updates to these codes	Incomplete and inaccurate updates, and overlooking new trends	In-house workgroup/committee, consult with external experts	To start
	Foster a culture of integrity through workshops and campaigns highlighting the societal impact of ethical research practices.	Engagement in integrity workshops and campaigns	Resource constraints	Partnerships with external partners to share resources and expertise	To start

Action No. 8: Promote improvements in the work environment

Roles & Responsibilities	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status
Pillars	Develop and promote European-level policy frameworks that support flexible work arrangements, research mobility, and an inclusive workplace culture.	Number of HEIs adopting these frameworks	National regulations limiting implementation	Align with national legislation and promote adaptation guidelines	Ongoing
	Define minimum standards for research infrastructure and wellbeing provisions across the alliance.	Shared standards approved by the Core team	Institutional resistance due to resource constraints	Provide phased implementation models and funding strategies	ongoing
	Integrate workplace wellbeing into E ³ UDRES ² strategic documents and evaluation tools.	Inclusion in strategic plans and evaluations	Low prioritisation in institutional agendas	Include well-being in performance indicators and alliance monitoring	Ongoing
Nexus	Organise cross-node workshops on improving work environments, focusing on shared challenges and solutions.	Number of joint events held per year	Limited engagement across institutions	Rotate facilitation and connect with other relevant nodes	To be done
	Establish a cross-institutional task force to collect, benchmark, and share workplace satisfaction data.	Number of institutions participating and data shared	Lack of harmonised metrics	Develop joint survey tools and reporting templates	To be done

	Coordinate access to upgraded infrastructure (labs, co-working spaces) across partner institutions.	Shared access agreements signed	Technical and administrative barriers	Pilot with 2–3 institutions before full rollout	Ongoing
	Mixed recruitment committees (and share job listing)	Recruitment committees should aim to include academic staff from the E ³ UDRES ² alliance when suitable.	National legislations might impose some restrictions, and partial compatibility of research and study domains	Mapping the national legislation restrictions.	To be done
Sparks	Launch pilot projects testing flexible scheduling, hybrid workspaces, or well-being programs (e.g., return-to-work support).	Number of pilots implemented	Poor participation or follow-up	Include feedback loops and link to institutional HR units	Ongoing
	Design and implement innovative researcher support tools (e.g., mobile career counselling, digital resource hubs).	Usage statistics and feedback	Low usage or visibility	Co-create with users and integrate in existing platforms	Ongoing/ to be done
	Prototype shared interdepartmental research environments or interdisciplinary hubs.	Number of prototypes piloted	Infrastructure mismatch	Use modular, scalable models adaptable across contexts	Ongoing/ to be done
Waves	Document and disseminate successful workplace improvement pilots via videos, reports, and peer learning events.	Number of outputs created and shared	Low outreach impact	Use storytelling and promote via E ³ UDRES ² channels	To be done
	Engage with external stakeholders (e.g., municipalities, NGOs, industry) to co-promote workplace wellbeing practices.	Number of external partners involved	Limited relevance beyond academia	Select transferable initiatives with cross-sectoral potential	To be done
	Showcase institutional transformations (e.g., sabbatical policy reforms, shared labs) as inspirational cases within the EU network.	Presentations at conferences or policy platforms	Insufficient visibility	Nominate ambassadors and create a showcase repository	To be done

ANNEX I | HRS4R award application process

Ent-r-e-novators Work Package 6 worked on one overarching milestone: the alignment of all partners’ human resources policies with the 40 principles of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (Charter & Code). This alignment was carried out through the development of customised action plans/HR strategies, and the European Commission granted recognition in the form of the prestigious “HR Excellence in Research Award.”

At the start of the project, only STPUAS held the “HR Excellence in Research Award.” During the project, the majority of institutions have already successfully received this recognition (ViA, IPS, UCLL, MATE), and UPT is actively progressing toward achieving it.

All institutions ensured that the application process for the HR Excellence in Research Award was collaborative and aligned with the alliance’s broader goals. A dedicated committee and working group—formed with attention to professional diversity and gender balance—coordinated the process, engaging researchers (R1–R4), HR specialists, and other stakeholders through surveys, interviews, and focus groups. The data collected was used to perform a comprehensive Gap Analysis across the four HRS4R pillars—Ethics and Integrity, Recruitment and Assessment, Working Conditions, and Career Development—and to co-create a detailed Action Plan. Throughout the process, surveys, webinars, workshops, open discussions and communication campaigns were used to inform and involve the academic community. At the same time, draft documents (Gap Analysis, Action Plan, OTM-R checklist) were reviewed and validated collaboratively. The resulting application was then submitted to EURAXESS, with further refinements made in response to feedback, strengthening both institutional alignment and ecosystem-wide impact. See Table 2.

Table 2 - HR Excellence in research award application process

Institution	Submission Date	Administrative Eligibility accepted	Initial Assessment	Award Status
UPT	July 21 st , 2024	July 22 nd , 2024	Oct 22 nd , 2024	In progress*
MATE	Sept 29 th , 2024	Sept 30 th , 2024	March 19 th , 2025	Award granted Sept 15 th , 2025
IPS	Sept 30 th , 2024	Nov 19 th , 2024	Jan 13 th , 2025	Award granted May 6 th , 2025
UCLL	Oct 15 th , 2024	Dec 4 th , 2024	Jan 13 th , 2025	Award granted July 3 rd , 2025
ViA	Sept 30 th , 2024	Nov 29 th , 2024	End of April, 2025	Award granted Aug 27 th , 2025

* Pending modifications – extended deadline (1 year). Review submitted June 11th – waiting for response.

This milestone significantly strengthens the E³UDRES² alliance by enhancing institutional credibility and international visibility, while also demonstrating a shared commitment to transparent, fair, and high-quality recruitment practices. It supports the creation of attractive career conditions for researchers and ensures that partners’ human resources policies are fully aligned with European standards and priorities. In doing so, the

alliance not only fosters a more sustainable and researcher-friendly environment but also increases its competitiveness in attracting top talent and securing external research funding, thereby reinforcing its long-term impact and reputation.

Through this achievement, E³UDRES² has moved closer to becoming a globally recognised, researcher-friendly alliance, committed to excellence, openness, and sustainability in higher education and research.

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